

Use of Keyline to increase soil chemicals conditions for plant assimilation

Introduction

The Montado is a multifunctional silvo-pastoral system with high conservation value, but which is currently subject to some pressure factors, namely the abandonment and intensification due to inadequate management of the animal herd in farms, among other factors.

Climate change is causing more frequent droughts and higher temperatures that result in the loss of soil organic matter, making soils more prone to erosion. This leads to loss of fertility, making the system more vulnerable to drought and less able to support the establishment of new trees. In response to these observations, the Operational Group ECOMONTADO XXI has tried to develop a new forest management practice to restore the vitality and productivity of Montado soils, based on the Keyline system and Agroecology.

The implementation of the Keyline system consists in the design of curves, slightly uneven (about 1%), in relation to the level curves, towards the ridge. In this way, the water is forced out of the valley area and distributed to areas where it normally does not accumulate. The Keyline system also includes the use of a Yeomans plow, which opens furrows in the soil without any mobilization, so as not to disturb soil life and reduce the rate of mineralization of organic matter to a minimum.

57 sampling points were defined for various measurements (soil quality, soil moisture monitoring, evaluation of pasture biomass growth and determination of species of pasture present). These points were grouped into straight lines with their beginning in a higher altitude topographical area and their end in a topographical area down.

Soil analyzes were carried out twice during the project, with the first soil collection taking place between March and May, 2019, and the second soil collection taking place between March and April, 2021. Soil samples were collected from 19 sampling sites, at the following depths (0-20 cm, 20-40 cm, 40-60 cm). Each sample from a location at a given depth is a composite sample of the samples collected at the two or three points (from the same location at that depth).

Analyzes of soil samples collected were: Field texture (only at the beginning of the project); pH (H₂O), pH (KCl), Conductivity, Organic Matter, Extractable Phosphorus (P₂O₅), Extractable Potassium (K₂O), Extractable Calcium, Extractable Magnesium and Manganese.

Lessons learned

There are a multitude of factors that influence the availability of different elements in the soil, namely pH values whose increase seems to have an impact on the highest phosphorus values observed. On the other hand, the growth of pasture biomass, quite significant in plot 1, but also observed in plots E and G where a Keyline passage, seems to influence the lower availability of potassium and calcium due to their absorption by the plants.

These results are in line with what has already been observed in other studies. In fact, Keyline was designed to improve water infiltration and prevent soil erosion which should, in the long term, increase soil fertility, but this result will take years to be observed. The increase in soil organic matter content can be a natural consequence of a good implementation of the Keyline design, without turning over the soil, but this too must be a process that will take several years to observe. The short period of study of this Operational Group does not allow the observation of these results or the clarification of the factors that justify the different variations in the contents of the different nutrients in the soil.

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Valores médios das primeiras análises de solos para as diferentes parcelas da exploração A (parcelas 1, 2 e 3) e da exploração B (parcelas 4 e 5) para as profundidades de 0 a 60 centímetros. * Profundidade de 0 a 10 centímetros.

Parcela	pH		Conductividade em H ₂ O (µS/cm)	P Extraível		K Extraível (mg/Kg)	Macronutrientes Extraíveis		Mn Extraível (mg/kg)	Textura			Classificação Textural	C _{org} (%)	Mat. Org. (%)	C _{org} (%*)	Mat. Org. (%*)
	H ₂ O	KCl 1M		Conc. Média	P ₂ O ₅ (mg/Kg)		Ca (mg/Kg)	Mg (mg/kg)		% Areia	% Limo	% Argila					
1	5,76	4,11	61,22	1,95	4,54	37,94	685,47	95,66	25,86	66,73	17,27	15,99	Franco-Arenoso	0,31	0,54	0,44	0,76
2	5,90	4,31	56,00	20,49	46,99	36,16	1232,37	450,79	24,72	60,74	13,86	25,40	Franco-Argiloso-Arenoso	0,20	0,34	0,28	0,48
3	5,82	4,11	112,00	13,30	30,58	33,77	2206,24	927,81	7,85	57,77	15,64	26,59	Franco-Argiloso-Arenoso	0,20	0,34	0,30	0,51
4	5,12	3,98	41,67	2,42	5,60	27,91	68,00	7,81	9,94	73,29	19,87	6,84	Franco-Arenoso	0,34	0,59	0,62	1,06
5	5,05	4,26	31,83	0,10	0,40	32,32	131,89	24,34	15,50	70,44	20,51	9,04	Franco-Arenoso	0,27	0,46	0,43	0,73
Valor médio em solos					51-100	51-100	430-860	71-124									

Figure 1. Results of soil analysis from the different plots.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<http://www.ecomontadoxxi.uevora.pt/>

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